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Fig S1. The dataset of 39 Trichoderma genomes contains 5 clades with different combinations of lifestyles and nutritional modes.

This consensus phylogenomic tree was created from 154 SCO IQ-TREES which had >98% BP, using 10,000 bootstraps. Values at nodes represent the IQ-TREE maximum likelihood BP, Internode Certainty (IC), and Internode Certainty All (ICA) (BP/IC/ICA). Internode Certainty (IC) and Internode Certainty All (ICA) values were obtained from the corresponding RAxML majority rule extended consensus tree. Species lifestyle is indicated by presence/absence of color-coordinated cell, nutritional mode is indicated by either a circle (saprotroph) or a star (mycotroph). Endophyte cells half-filled indicated a potential endophytic lifestyle for that species. Branch lengths are not proportional to sequence divergence.

Fig S2. Genome quality was not correlated with number of metabolic gene clusters identified.

Genome quality is not correlated with the number of (A) DGC families (Pearson's, $p > 0.05$) (B) BGC families (Pearson's, $p > 0.05$), and (C) number of metabolic genes (Pearson's, $p > 0.05$) identified in the *Trichoderma* genomes. Each point represents a *Trichoderma* isolate. Point fill indicates nutritional mode, point shape indicates the clade to which the isolate belongs, and color indicates whether the *Trichoderma* species is recorded as having an endophytic lifestyle. Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig S3. Genomes with greater numbers of DGCs also contained greater numbers of BGCs.

(A) The number of DGC families identified in each genome positively correlates with the number of identified biosynthetic gene cluster families (Pearson's, $p < 0.005$). (B) The proportion of DGC families to total number genes per genome positively correlates with the proportion of DGC families to total number genes per genome (Pearson's, $p < 0.005$). Each point represents a *Trichoderma* isolate. Point fill indicates nutritional mode, point shape indicates which clade to which the isolate belongs, and color indicates whether or not the isolate has a possible endophytic lifestyle. Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig S4. Larger genomes contain more gene clusters and metabolic genes.

There is a significant correlation between genome length (bp) of the 38 *Trichoderma* genomes and the diversity of (A) DGC families (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$), (B) BGC families (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$), and (C) proportion of metabolic genes to total genes (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$). Points highlighted in red are isolates identified to have an endophytic lifestyle, points in black did not have an identified endophytic lifestyle, and points in blue were species with a potential endophytic lifestyle. Mycotrophic genomes are represented by empty points, saprotrophic genomes are represented by filled points. Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig S5. Larger genomes contain a greater proportion of gene clusters to genes.

There is a significant correlation between genome length (bp) of the 38 *Trichoderma* genomes and the diversity of (A) proportion of biosynthetic genes to BGC clusters (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$) and (B) proportion of DGC families to total genes (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$). Points highlighted in red are isolates identified to have an endophytic lifestyle, points in black did not have an identified endophytic lifestyle, and points in blue were species with a potential endophytic lifestyle. Mycotrophic genomes are represented by empty points, saprotrophic genomes are represented by filled points. Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig S6. Genomes with more genes contain greater numbers of metabolic gene clusters.

The overall number of genes identified in a *Trichoderma* genome is correlated with the number of (A) identified DGCs (Pearson's, $p < 0.005$) and (B) BGCs (Pearson's, $p < 0.005$). Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig S7. Endophyte genomes contain greater numbers of metabolic gene clusters and mycoparasitism genes.

The average number metabolic gene clusters is significantly different between endophytic and non-endophytic *Trichoderma* genomes for both (A) DGCs (Wilcoxon, $p \leq 0.05$) and (B) BGCs (two-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.05$). There is no significant differences between the number of (C) chitinase genes for endophytic and non-endophytic *Trichoderma* genomes (Wilcoxon, $p > 0.05$). The number of mycoparasitism genes is significantly higher in (D) endophyte genomes (Wilcoxon, $p \leq 0.05$). (E) The number of metabolic genes per genome were higher in endophytes than in non-endophyte genomes (two-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.05$). The number of metabolic genes per BGC was not significantly different between endophyte and non-endophyte genomes (two-sample t-test, $p > 0.05$).

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Fig S8. Endophytic *Trichoderma* genomes contain significantly greater numbers of ARD, NAD, and FAD DGC. Differences between endophytic and non-endophytic DGC class counts were calculated using Wilcoxon rank sum test corrected with Holm-Bonferroni method. Endophytic genomes have significantly greater ARD, NAD, and FAD (each $p \leq 0.05$), significance differences between groups are indicated with an asterisk. No significant difference between endophyte and non-endophyte DGC count is indicated with “NS” ($p > 0.05$).

Fig S10. The distribution of individual DGC families is consistent with *Trichoderma* phylogeny.

All evaluated DGC families did not have a significant result when analyzing each DGC's Fritz and Purvis' D-statistic ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the distribution of DGC families followed Brownian motion evolution. The DGC families most overrepresented in endophyte genomes ($E:NE > 3$) are labeled. Black points in the shaded area of the graph would indicate DGC families which exhibit overdispersal in the *Trichoderma* phylogeny as well as overrepresentation in endophytic genomes.

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Fig S11. Metabolic gene cluster content and proportions vary among *Trichoderma* clades.

There are significant differences between the *Trichoderma* clades for total count of (A) DGCs per genome ($p \leq 0.05$) and (B) BGCs per genome ($p \leq 0.05$). There are also significant differences between clades for the (C) proportion of DGCs to total gene number in each genome ($p \leq 0.05$) and (D) proportion of BGCs to total gene number in each genome ($p \leq 0.05$). Significant differences were determined using Kruskal-Wallis test, post hoc differences were determined with Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction.

Fig S12: The number and distribution of different BGC families varies across the *Trichoderma* phylogeny.

Heat map showing presence/absence of biosynthetic gene cluster families for each *Trichoderma* genome. Singleton BGCs, as well as the highly fragmented *T. cf. atroviride* (LU140) genome, are included in this figure. The total number of BGC per genome, as well as the distribution of fungal-RiPP, other hybrid, and beta-lactone clusters, are unchanged from those in Fig 1 and are thus excluded for visualization purposes. Species lifestyle is indicated by presence/absence of color-coordinated cell, nutritional mode is indicated by either a circle (saprotroph) or a star (mycotroph). Endophyte cells half-filled indicated a potential endophytic lifestyle for that species

Fig S13. Endophytic genomes are enriched in T1PKS, NRPS-like, beta-lactone, and fungal-RiPP BGCs. Significant differences were determined by the Wilcoxon rank sum test corrected with Holm-Bonferroni method. No significant differences between groups are indicated by “NS”. Outliers within groups are labeled.

Fig S14. The distribution of most individual BGC families is consistent with *Trichoderma* phylogeny.

The majority of evaluated BGC families did not have a significant result when analyzing each's Fritz and Purvis' D-statistic ($p > 0.05$), which indicated Brownian motion evolution. The BGC families that did not exhibit Brownian motion model evolution were not found enriched in endophyte genomes (E:NE < 2). The BGC families most overrepresented in endophyte (E:NE value > 6) and DGCs overdispersed in the *Trichoderma* phylogeny (D-statistic > 1) are labeled. Black points in the shaded area of the graph would indicate BGC families which exhibit overdispersal in the *Trichoderma* phylogeny as well as overrepresentation in endophytic genomes.

Fig S15. Genomes with greater numbers of genes and larger genomes contain more mycoparasitism-related genes.

The total number of mycoparasitism genes per genome is positively correlated with (A) total genes in a Trichoderma genome (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$) and (B) genome length (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$). (C) There is no relation to genome quality (N50) and number of identified mycoparasitism-related genes per genome (Pearson's, $p > 0.05$). Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig 16. Metabolic gene clusters and mycoparasitism genes are enriched in mycotrophic genomes.

The average number of metabolic gene clusters is significantly different between mycotrophic and saprotrophic *Trichoderma* genomes for both A) DGCs (2-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.0005$) and B) BGCs (2-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.0005$). The total number of C) chitinase genes is higher in mycotrophic genomes (2-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.0005$), as are the D) total number of mycoparasitism genes (2-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.0005$). Outliers are labeled and significant differences are indicated with asterisks.

Fig S17. Some mycoparasitism genes are overrepresented in mycotrophs and overdispersed in *Trichoderma*.

A) The mycotroph to saprotroph gene ratio (M:S) and Blomberg's K value suggests that five mycoparasitism genes are overdispersed in *Trichoderma* ($K < 0.8$, $p > 0.05$) and enriched in genomes with a mycotrophic nutritional mode ($M:S > 2$).

B) The mycotroph to saprotroph gene ratio (M:S) and Blomberg's K value suggests that three mycoparasitism genes are overdispersed in *Trichoderma* ($\Lambda < 0.8$, $p > 0.05$) and enriched in genomes with a mycotrophic nutritional mode ($M:S > 2$). Black points in the shaded area of the graph would indicate mycoparasite genes which exhibit overdispersal in the *Trichoderma* phylogeny as well as overrepresentation in mycotrophic genomes.

Fig S18. Amount and percent of mycoparasitism-related genes differ between *Trichoderma* clades.

(A) Longibrachiatum contains the fewest amount of mycoparasitism-related genes while Virens and section Trichoderma contain the highest amount (Kruskal-Wallis, correction with Bonferroni, $p \leq 0.05$). (B) Harzianum, Longibrachiatum, and Virens contain the lowest percent of mycoparasitism genes to the total number of genes per genome, and Brevicompactum and section Trichoderma contains the highest (ANOVA, correction with Bonferroni, $p \leq 0.05$).

Fig S19. Phylogenetic correction of mycoparasitism data still indicate separation based on *Trichoderma* clade.

(A) Phylogenetic tree and relative signal of phylogenetically-corrected global principal component 1 (PC1) and global principal component 2 (PC2) for each *Trichoderma* genome. (B) Top 10 mycoparasitism genes contributing to PC1 signal and top 11 mycoparasitism genes contributing to PC2 signal. (C) Eigenvalues for the phylogenetic correction PCA (pPCA) global principal components (PCs).

Fig S20. *Trichoderma* genomes have similar mycoparasitism gene repertoires to other genomes within the same clade.

Principal components analysis (PCA) of the distribution of the 746 mycoparasitism-related genes; the inherent phylogenetic bias within the *Trichoderma* dataset was corrected with phylogenetic principal components analysis (pPCA). Plotting of the global principal components values for each genome shows that *Trichoderma* genomes are grouping based on *Trichoderma* clade rather than nutritional mode or lifestyle.

Fig S21. Larger genomes and genomes that contain more genes contain greater numbers of chitinase genes. The overall number of genes identified in a *Trichoderma* genome is correlated with the number of A) identified chitinase genes (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$) and B) genome length (Pearson's, $p \leq 0.05$), but not with C) genome quality (Pearson's, $p \geq 0.05$). Gray shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig S22. Endophytes only differ in chitinase BII gene/total gene proportion compared to non-endophytes.

(A) Endophyte genomes do not significantly differ in any chitinase class overall count when compared with non-endophyte genomes (Wilcoxon, $p > 0.05$) (B) (A) Endophyte genomes only have a significantly higher proportion of chitinase class BII genes to total genes per genome as compared to non-endophyte genomes (Wilcoxon, $p \leq 0.05$).

Fig S23. No chitinase classes are overrepresented in endophytic *Trichoderma* genomes.

Most evaluated chitinase class distributions were determined to be consistent with Brownian motion evolution as determined by their (A) Blomberg's K value and significance (p -value ≤ 0.05) and (B) Pagel's Lambda value and significance ($p \leq 0.05$). Black points in the shaded area of the graph would indicate chitinase gene classes which exhibit overdispersal in the *Trichoderma* phylogeny as well as overrepresentation in endophytic genomes.

Fig S24. Mycotrophs differ in both count and proportion of chitinase classes compared to saprotrophs. (A) Mycotroph genomes have significantly greater numbers of BI, BII, and CI class chitinase genes compared to saprotroph genomes (2-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.05$). (B) Saprotroph genomes have significantly greater percentage of total gene number for AII, AIV, AV, BI, BII, BV, CI, and CHITD class chitinase genes compared to mycotroph genomes (2-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.05$).

Fig S25. Most chitinase class distributions were consistent with *Trichoderma* phylogeny.

Most evaluated chitinase class distributions were determined to be consistent with Brownian motion evolution as determined by their (A) Blomberg's K value and significance (p -value ≤ 0.05) and (B) Pagel's Lambda value and significance ($p \leq 0.05$). Black points in the shaded area of the graph would indicate chitinase gene classes which exhibit overdispersal in the *Trichoderma* phylogeny as well as overrepresentation in mycotroph genomes.

Fig S26. Genomes in different *Trichoderma* clades differ in their chitinase gene content and proportion.

There are significant differences between *Trichoderma* clades in their (A) number of chitinase genes ($p \leq 0.05$) and (B) percent of chitinase genes ($p \leq 0.05$). Outlier genomes are labeled. Significant differences are indicated by different letters. Differences were calculated with ANOVA, post hoc tested with Tukey's HSD.

Fig S27. Trichoderma clades differ in total amount and proportion of LysM and CBD content.

(A) Virens has highest number of LysM and section Trichoderma has the fewest (ANOVA, corrected with Holm-Bonferroni, $p \leq 0.05$). (B) Virens has highest number of CBD; Brevicompectum and section Trichoderma have the fewest (ANOVA, corrected with Holm-Bonferroni, $p \leq 0.05$). (C) Section Trichoderma has the lowest percentage of LysM to total gene count (ANOVA, corrected with Holm-Bonferroni, $p \leq 0.05$). (D) Section Trichoderma has the lowest percentage of CBD to total gene count (ANOVA, corrected with Holm-Bonferroni, $p \leq 0.05$). Significant differences are indicated by different letters, as determined by Tukey's HSD.

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Fig S28. Domain architecture of the 26 chitinases in *T. endophyticum* strain PP24.

Chitinase classes are indicated according to (Goughenour 2020). GH-18 domains are represented by black ovals, chitin-binding domains (CBD) are represented as green pentagons, Lysin domains (LysM) are represented as orange hexagons, and an RTA1 Superfamily domain is represented by a blue cylinder.

Fig S29. *Trichoderma* genomes with multiple potential lifestyles have more metabolic gene clusters.

Genomes of *Trichoderma* species recorded as having multiple lifestyles have (A) a significantly greater diversity of DGC (two-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.05$) and (B) a significantly greater number of BGC (two-sample t-test, $p \leq 0.05$) as compared to genomes of *Trichoderma* species recorded as only having a single potential lifestyle.

Table S1. Species name, strain identifier, source of genomic reads, lifestyle information, nutritional mode, and geographic origin of each *Trichoderma* isolate used in this study.

Verified species name	Given species name	Assembly source (SRA accession)	Genome assembly accession	Strain	Nutritional mode	Lifestyle	Country of Origin	Lifestyle (Endophyte or non-endophyte)
<i>T. afroharzianum</i> *	<i>T. harzianum</i>	NCBI	GCA_000988865.1	T6776	mycotroph	fungi, soil	Italy	Endophyte
<i>T. afroharzianum</i> *	<i>T. viride</i>	NCBI (SRX751293)	This study	LTR-2	mycotroph	fungi, soil	China	Endophyte
<i>T. arundinaceum</i>	<i>T. arundinaceum</i>	NCBI	GCA_003012105.1	IBT 40837	saprotroph	soil	Iran	Non-endophyte
<i>T. asperellum</i>	<i>T. asperellum</i>	NCBI	GCA_000733085.2	B05	saprotroph	soil	France	Non-endophyte
<i>T. asperellum</i>	<i>T. asperellum</i>	NCBI	GCA_003025105.1	CBS 433.97	saprotroph	soil	United States	Non-endophyte
<i>T. atroviride</i>	<i>T. atroviride</i>	NCBI	GCA_001599035.1	JCM 9410	mycotroph	soil, wood/litter	Japan	Non-endophyte
<i>T. atroviride</i>	<i>T. atroviride</i>	NCBI	GCA_002916895.1	LY357	mycotroph	soil, wood/litter	China	Non-endophyte
<i>T. atroviride</i>	<i>T. atroviride</i>	NCBI	GCA_000963795.1	XS2015	mycotroph	soil, wood/litter	The Netherlands	Non-endophyte
<i>T. atroviride</i>	<i>T. atroviride</i>	NCBI	GCA_000171015.2	IMI 206040	mycotroph	soil, wood/litter	Sweden	Non-endophyte

Verified species name	Given species name	Assembly source (SRA accession)	Genome assembly accession	Strain	Nutritional mode	Lifestyle	Country of Origin	Lifestyle (Endophyte or non-endophyte)
<i>T. bissettii</i> *	<i>T. koningii</i>	NCBI	GCA_001950475.1	JCM 1883	saprotroph	only known from a human sinus cavity	Wales	Non-endophyte
<i>T. brevicompactum</i>	<i>T. brevicompactum</i>	NCBI	GCA_003012085.1	IBT 40841	saprotroph	endophyte, soil	Iran	Endophyte
<i>T. cf. atroviride</i>	<i>T. cf. atroviride</i>	NCBI (SRX1601956)	This study	LU132	mycotroph	soil, wood/litter	New Zealand	Non-endophyte
<i>T. cf. atroviride</i>	<i>T. cf. atroviride</i>	NCBI (SRX1605616)	This study	LU140	mycotroph	soil, wood/litter	New Zealand	Non-endophyte
<i>T. citrinoviride</i>	<i>T. citrinoviride</i>	NCBI	GCA_003025115.1	TUCIM 6016	saprotroph	wood/litter	Unknown	Non-endophyte
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	<i>T. endophyticum</i>	This study	This study	LA10	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Peru	Endophyte
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	<i>T. endophyticum</i>	This study	This study	LA29	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Peru	Endophyte
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	<i>T. endophyticum</i>	This study	This study	PP24	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Peru	Endophyte

Verified species name	Given species name	Assembly source (SRA accession)	Genome assembly accession	Strain	Nutritional mode	Lifestyle	Country of Origin	Lifestyle (Endophyte or non-endophyte)
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	<i>T. endophyticum</i>	This study	This study	PP89	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Peru	Endophyte
<i>T. gamsii</i>	<i>T. gamsii</i>	NCBI	GCA_002894205.1	A5MH	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Australia	Endophyte
<i>T. gamsii</i>	<i>T. gamsii</i>	NCBI	GCA_001481775.2	T6085	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Ukraine	Endophyte
<i>T. guizhouense</i>	<i>T. guizhouense</i>	NCBI	GCA_002022785.1	NJAU 4742	mycotroph	fungi, wood/litter	China	Endophyte
<i>T. hamatum</i>	<i>T. hamatum</i>	NCBI	GCA_000331835.2	GD12	saprotroph	soil	England	Endophyte
<i>T. harzianum</i>	<i>T. harzianum</i>	NCBI	GCA_001990665.1	B97	mycotroph	soil	France	Non-endophyte
<i>T. harzianum</i>	<i>T. harzianum</i>	NCBI	GCA_003025095.1	CBS 226.95	mycotroph	soil	England	Non-endophyte
<i>T. koningiopsis</i>	<i>T. koningiopsis</i>	NCBI	GCA_002246955.1	POS7	mycotroph	endophyte, soil	Argentina	Endophyte
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	NCBI	GCA_003025155.1	ATCC 18648	saprotroph	soil	United States	Non-endophyte
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	NCBI	GCA_000332775.1	SMF2	saprotroph	soil	China	Non-endophyte

Verified species name	Given species name	Assembly source (SRA accession)	Genome assembly accession	Strain	Nutritional mode	Lifestyle	Country of Origin	Lifestyle (Endophyte or non-endophyte)
<i>T. parareesei</i>	<i>T. parareesei</i>	NCBI	GCA_001050175.1	CBS 125925	saprotroph	wood/litter	Argentina	Non-endophyte
<i>T. pleuroticola</i> *	<i>T. harzianum</i>	NCBI	GCA_002894145.1	Tr1	mycotroph	fungi	China	Non-endophyte
<i>T. reesei</i>	<i>T. reesei</i>	NCBI	GCA_001999515.1	CBS 999.97	saprotroph	wood/litter	French Guiana	Non-endophyte
<i>T. reesei</i>	<i>T. reesei</i>	NCBI	GCA_002006585.1	QM6a	saprotroph	wood/litter	Solomon Islands	Non-endophyte
<i>T. reesei</i>	<i>T. reesei</i>	NCBI (SRX059777)	This study	QM 9136	saprotroph	wood/litter	Mutant derived from QM6a	Non-endophyte
<i>T. reesei</i>	<i>T. reesei</i>	NCBI (SRX060131)	This study	QM 9978	saprotroph	wood/litter	Mutant derived from QM6a	Non-endophyte
<i>T. reesei</i>	<i>T. reesei</i>	NCBI	GCA_000513815.1	RUT C30	saprotroph	wood/litter	United States	Non-endophyte
<i>T. simmonsii</i> *	<i>T. virens</i>	NCBI	GCA_001931985.1	IMV 00454	mycotroph	fungi, wood/litter	Ukraine	Endophyte
<i>T. virens</i>	<i>T. virens</i>	NCBI	GCA_000800515.1	FT 333	mycotroph	fungi, soil, wood/litter	Taiwan	Non-endophyte
<i>T. virens</i>	<i>T. virens</i>	NCBI	GCA_001835465.1	IMI 304061	mycotroph	fungi, soil, wood/litter	India	Non-endophyte

Verified species name	Given species name	Assembly source (SRA accession)	Genome assembly accession	Strain	Nutritional mode	Lifestyle	Country of Origin	Lifestyle (Endophyte or non-endophyte)
<i>T. virens</i>	<i>T. virens</i>	NCBI	GCA_000170995.2	Gv29.8	mycotroph	fungi, soil, wood/litter	Unknown	Non-endophyte
<i>Trichoderma sp.*</i>	<i>T. harzianum</i>	NCBI (SRX1433332)	This study	OTPB3	mycotroph	unknown	India	Non-endophyte

*Some isolates were previously identified as different species but were re-identified for this study.

Table S2. Genome statistics of the 39 Trichoderma isolates.

Verified species name	Strain	Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (%)	Number genes (post-Orthofiller)	N50	Genome length (Mb)
<i>T. arundinaceum</i>	IBT 40837	96.7	10,658	61,935	36.9
<i>T. asperellum</i>	B05	96.4	11,676	99,299	37.7
<i>T. asperellum</i>	CBS 433.97	98.8	11,666	2,128,412	37.5
<i>T. atroviride</i>	JCM 9410	98.9	11,600	5,619,901	37.3
<i>T. cf. atroviride</i>	LU132	72.7	12,669	9,580	35.4
<i>T. cf. atroviride</i>	LU140	61.2	8,243	5,723	33.7

Verified species name	Strain	Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (%)	Number genes (post-Orthofiller)	N50	Genome length (Mb)
<i>T. atroviride</i>	LY357	98.5	11,565	100,133	35.9
<i>T. atroviride</i>	XS2015	98.9	11,722	2,105,403	36.4
<i>T. atroviride</i>	IMI 206040	98.7	11,624	2,007,903	36.1
<i>T. brevicompactum</i>	IBT 40841	97.4	10,764	58,500	37.0
<i>T. citrinoviride</i>	TUCIM 6016	95.5	9,918	1,846,965	33.2
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	LA10	99.0	12,619	1,095,838	39.2
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	LA29	99.0	12,635	1,266,890	39.2
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	PP24	99.0	12,608	713,317	38.9
<i>T. endophyticum</i>	PP89	99.1	12,606	1,414,947	38.9
<i>T. gamsii</i>	A5MH	98.7	11,567	594,470	38.5
<i>T. gamsii</i>	T6085	98.8	11,893	697,391	37.9

Verified species name	Strain	Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (%)	Number genes (post-Orthofiller)	N50	Genome length (Mb)
<i>T. guizhouense</i>	NJAU 4742	98.1	12,438	2,414,983	38.3
<i>T. harzianum</i>	B97	98.3	12,806	113,316	40.7
<i>T. harzianum</i>	CBS 226.95	98.8	12,920	2,414,909	41.0
<i>Trichoderma sp.</i>	OTPB3	98.1	12,777	142,666	42.0
<i>T. afroharzianum</i>	T6776	98.0	12,418	68,846	39.7
<i>T. pleuroticola</i>	Tr1	98.1	11,921	626,242	38.8
<i>T. hamatum</i>	GD12	97.9	11,572	179,274	38.4
<i>T. bissettii</i>	JCM 1883	98.5	9,242	4,316,785	32.3
<i>T. koningiopsis</i>	POS7	97.4	11,405	1,749,579	36.6
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	ATCC 18648	87.5	9,789	1,606,350	32.2
<i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	SMF2	98.4	9,854	863,071	31.7

Verified species name	Strain	Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (%)	Number genes (post-Orthofiller)	N50	Genome length (Mb)
<i>T. parareesei</i>	CBS 125925	97.1	9,578	68,608	32.1
<i>T. reesei</i>	CBS 999.97	98.6	9,844	1,217,941	32.5
<i>T. reesei</i>	QM6a	99.0	9,839	5,311,445	34.9
<i>T. reesei</i>	QM 9136	97.8	9,963	60,397	32.6
<i>T. reesei</i>	QM 9978	97.9	9,918	61,591	33.0
<i>T. reesei</i>	RUT C30	98.8	9,815	1,023,047	32.7
<i>T. virens</i>	FT 333	98.1	12,734	173,918	38.6
<i>T. virens</i>	IMI 304061	98.8	14,297	722,602	45.8
<i>T. afroharzianum</i>	LTR-2	98.8	11,362	92,065	38.2
<i>T. simmonsii</i>	IMV 00454	98.5	12,733	1,319,489	42.0
<i>T. virens</i>	Gv29.8	99.0	12,664	1,836,662	39.0

Table S3. Mycoparasitism gene orthogroups of interest found in the highest endophyte:non-endophyte ratio.

Mycoparasitism Gene orthogroup	Pagel's Lambda	Pagel's Lambda p-value	Blomberg's K	Blomberg's K p-value	M:S*	E:NE**	Eggnog Annotation
OG0010098	0.999	8.71E-12	0.325	0.001	9.130	4.714	Unknown Function
OG0000661	0.917	1.11E-08	0.334	0.001	4.099	3.143	Function unknown (NAD(P)H-binding)
OG0009104	0.921	5.62E-08	0.0140	0.082	4.783	3.048	Unknown Function
OG0010147	0.999	2.38E-17	0.471	0.001	4.565	2.857	Function unknown (Zinc Finger)
OG0009580	0.999	2.50E-30	2.99	0.001	13.043	2.786	Post-translational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones (Eukaryotic aspartyl protease)
OG0009038	0.999	2.16E-10	0.230	0.002	3.587	2.743	Unknown Function
OG0009716	0.999	7.65E-20	0.817	0.001	3.261	2.694	Unknown Function
OG0008134	0.961	1.59E-07	0.004	0.284	6.522	2.637	Unknown Function (X-Pro dipeptidyl-peptidase C-terminal non-catalytic domain)
OG0010671	0.780	0.00094367	0.0324	0.02	1.304	2.400	Unknown Function
OG0009627	0.161	0.211	0.039	0.009	2.446	2.357	Unknown Function

*Ratio of gene count in mycotroph to saprotroph *Trichoderma* genomes

**Ratio of gene count in endophytic to non-endophytic *Trichoderma* genomes

Table S4. Mycoparasitism gene orthogroups of interest found in the highest mycotroph:saprotroph ratios as well as orthogroups only found in mycotrophs.

Mycoparasitism Gene orthogroup	Pagel's Lambda	Pagel's Lambda p-value	Blomberg's K	Blomberg's K p-value	M:S*	E:NE**	Eggnog Annotation
OG0008901	0.99	7.14E-24	1.029	0.001	--***	1.978	Amino acid transport and metabolism (Amino acid transport and metabolism)
OG0009237	0.99	1.23E-21	0.830	0.001	--	1.714	Unknown Function (LamB/YcsF family)
OG0009490	0.999	4.45E-28	1.997	0.001	--	1.558	Unknown Function (spectrin binding)
OG0010126	0.999	1.31E-23	0.93	0.001	--	1.714	Unknown Function
OG0010265	0.999	4.53E-41	8.061	0.001	--	1.959	Carbohydrate transport and metabolism (glycerone kinase activity)
OG0010647	0.999	3.14E-14	0.304	0.001	--	2.000	Unknown Function (Domain of unknown function DUF3328)
OG0011909	0.999	1.12E-24	1.617	0.001	--	1.286	No orthologs found
OG0011914	0.817	0.00596218	0.050	0.031	--	0.686	Unknown Function
OG0012676	0.999	5.02E-23	1.307	0.001	--	0.429	Unknown Function
OG0012734	0.999	5.02E-23	1.307	0.001	--	0.429	Nucleotide transport and metabolism, Translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis (phospholipid biosynthetic process)
OG0013241	0.999	8.90E-15	0.410	0.001	--	0.000	Unknown Function (zinc finger)
OG0014884	0.999	2.87E-09	0.252	0.016	--	0.000	Unknown Function (Heterokaryon incompatibility protein (HET))
OG0016824	0.096	0.35427001	0.020	0.383	--	0.000	Post-translational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones (Belongs to the peptidase C1 family)
OG0009580	0.999	2.50E-30	2.99	0.001	13.043	2.786	Post-translational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones (Eukaryotic aspartyl protease)
OG0009990	0.999	5.95E-22	0.848	0.001	10.434	1.929	Unknown Function

OG0010098	0.999	8.71E-12	0.325	0.001	9.130	4.714	Unknown Function
OG0002822	0.999	1.34E-19	0.68	0.001	7.826	2.000	Unknown Function (Serine hydrolase) (FSH1)
OG0009146	0.999	7.54E-11	0.224	0.001	7.500	1.857	Translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis (amidase C869.01)
OG0008134	0.961	1.59E-07	0.004	0.284	6.521	2.63	Unknown Function (X-Pro dipeptidyl-peptidase C-terminal non-catalytic domain)
OG0009419	0.999	9.95E-23	1.014	0.001	6.522	1.714	Carbohydrate transport and metabolism, Cell wall/membrane/envelope biogenesis (NmrA-like family)
OG0008747	0.564	0.00033682	0.267	0.001	5.652	2.110	Function unknown (TAP-like protein)
OG0008746	0.99	1.70E-14	0.307	0.001	5.435	1.486	Unknown Function
OG0011291	0.747	2.51E-06	0.01	0.167	5.217	1.371	Unknown Function
OG0011298	0.999	3.12E-05	0.12	0.002	5.217	2.143	Unknown Function

*Ratio of gene count in mycotrophic to saprotrophic *Trichoderma* genomes

**Ratio of gene count in endophytic to non-endophytic *Trichoderma* genomes

***Gene orthogroups that were not detected in saprotrophic genomes are designated with a "--" in place of a mycotroph:saprotroph ratio.

Table S5. Placement of *Brevicompactum* clade ergot alkaloid BGC gene phylogenies

Gene	In clade of predominantly Hypocreales spp.	In clade of predominantly Xylariales spp.	Node support	Noteworthy results
Tribre1_123771 elymojavine monooxygenase (<i>cloA</i>)	X	-	100	<i>Brevicompactum</i> clade is sister to other Hypocreales
Tribre1_123772 Chanoclavine synthase catalase (<i>easC</i>)	-	-		Other <i>Trichoderma</i> in a clade with a homolog of tribre1 query gene

Tribre1_123773 Lysergyl peptide synthetase subunit 2 (<i>lps2</i>)	-	-		
Tribre1_123774 chanoclavine-I dehydrogenase (<i>easD</i>)	-	X	96	aspcor2, psevol1 within clade
Tribre1_123775 Chanoclavine-I aldehyde oxidoreductase (<i>easA</i>)	-	X	100	aspcor2, psevol1 within clade, Pleosporales in outgroup
Tribre1_123776 argoclavine dehydrogenase (<i>easG</i>)	-	X	95	aspcor2 sister to clade
Tribre1_123777 chanoclavine-I synthase oxidoreductase (<i>easE</i>)	-	X	100	aspcor2, psevol1 within clade
Dimethylallyltryptophan N-methyltransferase (<i>easF</i>)	-	X	100	aspcor2, psevol1 within clade
Tribre1_123778 Dimethylallyltryptophan synthase (<i>dmaW</i>)	-	X	100	aspcor2 within clade; bipsor1.1, cocsat1 (Pleosporales) in clade. Pleosporales have 100 support with Xylariales sp. (<i>mictri1</i>)

Tribre1_123779 hypothetical protein	-	X	100	Absent from Clavicipitaceae, largely recovered in Xylariales, other Trichoderma in the sameclade, 1 copy/genome
Tribre1_123780 oxygenase (<i>easH</i>)	-	X	100	aspcor2, parnod1.1, epifes1.1 in clade
Tribre1_123781 Lysergyl peptide synthetase subunit 1 (<i>lps1</i>)	-	X	52	aspcor2, epifes1.1 in clade

Table S6. Functional annotations of the top 21 mycoparasitism genes contributing to the global PC1 and PC2 in the pPCA analysis.

Orthogroup	Functional Category	Description
OG0000020	Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport, and catabolism	Enoyl-(Acyl carrier protein) reductase
OG0009047	Function unknown	--
OG0008954	Function unknown	oligopeptide transmembrane transporter activity
OG0009301	Function unknown	--
OG0008688	Translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis	maturation of LSU-rRNA
OG0000599	Function unknown	--
OG0008901	Amino acid transport and metabolism	glutamine biosynthetic process
OG0000008	Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport, and catabolism	phosphopantetheine binding
OG0000642	Post-translational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones	Belongs to the peptidase S1 family
OG0010265	Carbohydrate transport and metabolism	glycerone kinase activity
OG0011331	Defense mechanisms	ATPase activity

OG0011314	Function unknown	--
OG0011345	Function unknown	--
OG0008929	Function unknown	--
OG0008903	Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	alkaline phosphatase activity
OG0008978	Function unknown	trichodiene synthase activity
OG0001105	Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	O-methyltransferase activity
OG0001172	Energy production and conversion	alpha-methylacyl-CoA racemase activity
OG0000193	Defense mechanisms	ATPase activity
OG0000045	Function unknown	--
OG0000267	Function unknown	--